

LINGUISTIC GENDEROLOGY. GENDER LINGUISTICS IN UZBEK

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Speech is a perfect event. How the speech is manifested depends not only on the speaker, the speech situation, but also on the speaker's gender. Women's speech is different from men's speech. Emotionality, subjective evaluation is more common in women's speech compared to men's. "Linguistic genderology" explains the gender differences in speech.

Linguistic genderology mainly covers two issues:

1. Gender reflection in language; The main goal of this approach is to study how the presence of people of different genders is manifested in language, how men and women are valued, and how they affect which areas of linguistics.
2. Speech and in general, the communicative behavior of men and women is organized by what means and under what conditions, how social factors and the communicative environment (for example, globalization) influence this process.

Basically, gender linguistics was created in the mid-90s of XX century. If we look at the sources created in that period, generalology is basically different in terms of style. The first serious works in this field were the works of linguistic anthropologists in the 40s and 50s. The first studies were recorded in E. Spear's work "Language, culture and personality" written in 1949. In the work, the researcher analyzed the language of the Indians of the Yann tribe and compared the speech of men and women and differentiated the concept of gender. In the tribe, he notes the elements of "masculine" and "feminine" slang.

In particular, we can see the gender difference not only in foreign languages, but in the speech of languages close to us, as well as in our own speech. As an example, let's take the lexeme "Kuda", in the current explanatory dictionary, this lexeme is defined as "parents of the groom and the bride (in relation to each other)". The lexeme "Kudagay" is defined as "Khotin kuda". Little by little, it seems that the affix "-gay" in ancient times indicated belonging to women.

In the history of gender linguistics, in 1978, the language of the Muschojin Indians in the southwestern state of Louisiana in America is an example. Only the older women of the U tribe spoke the same language as the men, and the young people, who preserved the features of female speech, spoke the same way as men, because women and men began to work together in the tribe.

We emphasize that the real genderology developed after the development of sociolinguistics. Because the age, gender, and cultural differences in people's speech have increased. Just like now, our older grandparents don't understand some of the jargon in the language of our youth. Even then, this misunderstanding may have occurred between the sexes.

In previous years in New York, there was a difference between the five phonetic variants of the "-ing" combination between men and women. This observation was made by V. Labov (1966).

In 1974, Maccoby and Jacklin, famous psychologists, considered the difference in the speech of women and men to be very contradictory.

I know that in Japanese, the difference in speech between men and women is evident when they call the same thing by different names. Women working in the government work speak a man's language, giving up the "women's language". Generally speaking, men's language is at the level of literary language for them. Women's language is an example of dialect.

Genderology in Uzbek

Eastern women have been distinguished by their delicate nature, gentleness, and manners since ancient times. I can give an example of my statement that in the speech of women, the situation of calling the husband and his relatives, especially the spouse, by name is almost never found. Our women can refer to their husbands as "daddy" and "dadajonisi". This is one of the features of women's speech. We hardly find this element in men's speech. In some cases, the reason for some joy, similar words of encouragement are found in men's speech. This situation is similar to the Indian term "Babu" for a man. "Babu" is used only for men. This is a feature of women's speech. In some cases, the affix "ji" can also be added. "Babuji" is used to refer to elders or highly respected male relatives. From this it is understood that the Indian language also has elements characteristic of our language.

Also, in our language, some slang and curse words characteristic of women's speech are almost never found in men's speech and in other languages. Women can speak faster and more expressively than men. Women "swallow" the end of the sentence, and men do the opposite. In the speech of Oyim Aftob in Abdulla Qadiri's novel "Gone Days".

"- I can't turn back your opinion by going against a work that you have agreed to, because after all, you have a patronymic name, and more discretion is in your hands."

In this example, the word fatherhood is spoken only to a man. This word does not correspond to the female gender, that is, the term "maternity" does not exist. The intonation characteristic of women's speech is very different from that of men. At the same time, words such as "aylanay", "girgitton", "orgilay", "qoqindiql" characteristic of the speech of a number of Uzbek women are lexical tools that express the subtlety of a positive meaning. They are mostly left by older women. For example;

- Yes, now when an old woman can do something like that.
- Come on, girgitton, let your grandmother take care of you.
- Yes, because of you, we stumbled
- Come on, come on, move faster now.

In the book "The Art of Conciliation" by our respected linguist Siddiq Momin, information is given about the work of Russian linguists Vladimir Nalivkin and his husband V.M. Nalivkina "Essays on marriage by the women of the isolated population of Fargona". In this collection of essays, the folk phrase "a woman who has passed through a sieve has fifty words" is scientifically explained. Of course, this does not mean that the woman who asked her neighbor for a sieve will talk a lot. It is explained that the situation of a woman who goes out to ask for a sieve will increase to fifty mouths because of the consequences of asking for her relatives.

In Uzbekistan, scientists such as A. Morozova, I. Tokhtasinov and G. Ergashova took steps towards gender linguistics. A. Morozova analyzes the issue of "masculinity" and "femininity" based on the Spanish language in gender linguistics. I. Tokhtasinov organizes male and female physical elements that remain in the artistic texts in English and Uzbek. G. Ergashova explained the concepts of male and female characteristic of phraseological and peremiological systems in English and Uzbek.

One of the main concepts of gender linguistics is the term gender stereotypes. Gender stereotypes are a system of all characteristics characteristic of a woman or a man. Such patterns characteristic of the Uzbek language can be seen in the language of artistic works, in particular, in the example of the work "Shaytanat". There are two types of stereotypes.

1. Gender stereotypes related to appearance;
2. Gender stereotypes related to character traits

Important gender stereotypes include the name, nickname, and character of the protagonist in speech or work. There are signs in the work that indicate whether

it is a woman or a man. Gender stereotypes found in the work can be divided into two types.

1. Male gender stereotypes
2. Gender stereotypes specific to women.

"Mother is not oppressed", "Johnon", "Mushfiq", "Masuma", "Khusroy", "witch" Expressions like "young man" are used only for women. their alternative is good for the male gender!

It is known that verbs such as "He touches his soul", "Noz-u karashma", "To live in a hurry", "Togkan" are related to the female gene.

A young man is holding his head by the window.

Onta turns a woman who has given birth into a girl whose mother did not love her.

We can find the manifestation of gender in the speech of adjusting the characteristics in the following two ways.

1. My mother blinked her eyes for a moment and asked slowly, panting, - What, opovsi?

In the following passage taken from the work "The World's Works", we can see that the lexeme "opovsi" is used referring to a woman.

He treated himself as "Opovsi".

You can find such things only in our store, brother. In this example, the lexeme "brother" also expressed the attitude of the adjuster towards himself.

2. - Where is your sister? I think you can send it anywhere, dear. In this sentence, the lexeme "opovsi" is used as an exhortation.

In this sentence, we understand from the lexeme "opovsi" that the listener is a woman.

In conclusion, we should emphasize that the linguistic expression of the differences in the speech, outlook, and culture of men and women are important aspects of gender linguistics!!!

List of used books:

- 1.V.Lobov "Til o`rganish. Ingliz o`qtuvchilarining milliy kengashi" P.187-221
- 2.Makkabi and Jaklin "Jinsiy farqlar psixologiyasi"
- 3.S.Mymin`s "Sozlashish san`ati"
4. " Gender munosabatlar nazariyasi va amaliyotiga kirish"
- 5.Tohir Malik "Shaytanat" V book P.187 III book P.201
6. "Dunyoning ishlari" Utkir KHoshimov
- 7.Internet sites.